

METHODS OF OPTIMIZING THE TECHNICAL TRAINING OF BELT WRESTLERS

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Annatology: This article describes the optimization of technical and tactical training of belt wrestlers, the elimination of errors in the training of belt wrestlers in technical movements, the main methods of optimizing technical training, the stages of improving the skills and qualifications of belt wrestlers.

Keywords: belt fighting, technical and tactical training, technical actions, movement skills and qualifications, optimization, improvement.

Optimization of technical training of skilled fighters is of great importance in modern sports, in which a combination of scientific and practical approaches is used. The main goal of optimizing technical training is to ensure that the athlete has a high level of performance and flexibility in relation to the opponent. Today, this process requires the use of many innovative technologies and methodologies. The main goal of optimization is to improve the technical training of the fighter and not be limited only to general movements, but to study the opponent, make decisions that correspond to each situation, choose the correct and effective methods. This process requires the application of scientific methodologies, tactical approaches, and innovative technologies. It also includes specialized training aimed at optimizing the technical training of qualified wrestlers, providing an individual approach to training, identifying athlete's weaknesses and developing them. In the process, the athlete is taught to adapt to changing conditions by self-assessment, analyzing the opponent's movements, periodically checking his technical skills.

In his research, M.A. Karpov has deeply studied methods for the formation of effective and flexible technical skills to develop athletes' ability to quickly adapt to an opponent's movements. At the same time, it emphasizes the need to adopt technical tactical approaches that are appropriate to the individual abilities of athletes. This study will help athletes to provide a high level of training, master their strategies for coping with different opponents, and identify the most effective pathways to achieve optimal results [1; 19 b].

Also, according to Kerimov F.A., general and special technical training of wrestlers are distinguished. General technical training focuses on acquiring a

variety of movement skills and skills in auxiliary sports, while special technical training focuses on acquiring technical skills in sports wrestling. [2; 240-245-b].

Technical skill in the Kerimov F.A training means excellent mastery of the most effective movement technique in the toughest conditions of sports competitions. There are three stages to improve technical skills:

Figure 1. Stages of improvement of technical preparation

At the first stage, technical training is aimed at the formation of a new technique of competitive movements, improving the conditions for its mastery in practice, studying (or restudy) some movements included in the system of competitive movements.

At the second stage, technical training is aimed at deep mastering and strengthening all skills of competitive movements.

At the third stage, technical training is aimed at improving the formed skills, expanding their variability, stability and reliability, in accordance with the conditions of the main competitions, the main tasks of each stage of technical training are:

1. Ensuring high stability and rational variability of movement skills that make up the wrestling technique, increasing their effectiveness in competitive conditions.

2. Partial reconstruction of movement skills, improvement of some methods taking into account the requirements of competition activities.

To solve the first task, the method of complicating external conditions, the method of exercises performed in different states of the body state is used. To solve the second task - the method of facilitation of the conditions for performing technical actions, the method of simultaneous exposure [2; 240-245-b, 3; 120-128 b] is used.

There are a number of ways to complicate external conditions when performing technical methods: The conditioned opponent's resistance methodology helps the wrestler improve the structure and rhythm of performing the technical move, achieving stability and efficiency faster.

The method to facilitate the conditions for performing technical actions includes several methodological methods:

1. Methodical method of separating the element of action. For example, in freestyle wrestling - to perform a grip on the upper body of the loin.

2. A methodical method of reducing muscle tension allows the wrestler to fine-tune certain movements in the skill of movement. To improve technical movements, a fighter is chosen for himself an opponent in a lightweight category.

3. A quick information method helps to quickly master the required width, rhythm, speed of movement, activates the process of understanding the action performed.

Artikov Z.S. believes that the technique of belt wrestlers forms the basis of a wrestler's skills and in many respects determines his capabilities. There are dozens of methods and types of belt wrestling. But this does not mean that one has to know all the methods perfectly [4; 60-63 b].

Mirzakulov Sh.A. As the athlete learns new methods, methods of countermeasures and methods of defense, the methods that fit his specific characteristics and habits and perform successfully will later be included in the plan of further improvement [5; 23-84-b].

Comprehensive technical training of a belt wrestler is one of the most important requirements for the level of development of modern sports.

Also, when choosing a strong technical action, the following rules should be observed:

1. Master technical actions, which are successfully calculated in the rules of the current competition;

2. Mastering the techniques, counter techniques and defensive options that best suit the athlete's specific characteristics from a variety of techniques;

1. Selection of technical actions that will give a good result in the fight against them, taking into account the technical capabilities of key competitors;

2. More emphasis on technical actions that expand access to previously learned methods and counter techniques;

3. It is necessary to master the basics of technique and the general rhythm of movement, eliminating moderate movements and excessive muscle tension;

4. The study of methods should be concentrated at a certain interval. Because long breaks between sessions reduce its impact. On the other hand, it is also not advisable to overrepetition of methods during one session, since the

development of coordination skills is mainly associated with overcoming difficulties that quickly exhaust the nervous system;

5. In order to avoid technical conditions that arise due to the lack of sufficient physical conditions, it is necessary to organize at a high level special physical training, corresponding to the dynamic characteristics of movements.

It is also important to identify mistakes that occur when making efforts to improve the technical skills of the wrestler, as well as to identify their causes. Timely elimination of such errors is important for the effectiveness of the technical improvement process.

All errors that occur in the process of learning motion are divided into the

Figure 2. Errors that occur in the process of learning motion

following groups:

To succeed in wrestling, an athlete must always be willing to adapt to the changing tactics of the opponent. In each fight, unique tactics are used, and it is imperative for the athlete to well monitor the behavior of his opponent, to study and to be flexible in coping with it. For example, if an opponent has strong grips, the athlete must quickly adopt new strategies that require a change in position or simplification of movements.

Conclusion: Repetition and regular exercises are essential for the development of technical and tactical skills in wrestling. By performing repetition while learning and mastering new movements, the movements become automatic. Through such exercises, the athlete achieves the perfect performance of each technique. Also, when using new tactics, the ability to react and make specific decisions through constant exercise develops. Goal-oriented exercises are essential in the development of wrestlers' technical and tactical skills. Every workout should focus on reinforcing the athlete's own weaknesses. For example, if a wrestler wants to perfect his short-distance movements, then

he should perform special short-distance wrestling techniques and exercises that develop quick decision-making.

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